

**THE INFLUENCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES ON ECONOMIC
DEVELOPMENT OF KABAROLE DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT

This study was sought necessary in the context of Kabarole. The report addresses the influence of small and medium enterprises on the economic development of Kabarole district, a case study of Kiko town council. It was guided by the following objectives; To find out the determinants for SMEs growth, to find out the contributions of small and medium enterprises on the economic development of Kabarole District, and lastly to find out the challenges faced by the small and medium enterprises in Kabarole District. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design and a sample of 50 SMEs was considered however 48 respondents actively participated in the exercise. The study adopted both a questionnaire and observation as the primary data collection tools.

The research project found out that the majority of SMEs employed more males than females who were educated to tertiary/university level. SMEs with educated people greatly had an impact on business sales. Managers and/or owners with experience and their respective businesses aided to sale more however most of the businesses didn't have strategies to guide their operation which would harm the growth of the business. SMEs have a great impact on Kiko through casual and office work however, unemployment in Kiko was high due to the growing population and some SMEs were not sure if they could employ more people. The poverty levels seemed to be covered up through the casual work however the number of SMEs could not unleash that problem due to population growth and the initiation of SMEs operating as clinics contributed to the health sector in Kiko. SMEs in Kiko were greatly limited by access to credit and lack of training that imposed doubt on managerial competence. Other challenges like limited capital, narrow customer base, poor infrastructure, and high taxes that drained their profits were other challenges that were cited. Policy makers should either support the local entrepreneurs to boost employment creation as a result poverty rate will reduce, the health sector in Kiko has to be improved and SMEs have to begin training and strategy formulation to aid the managers and/or owners.

Financial providers have to assist SMEs to raise finance if the goal of economic development is to be achieved at all levels through employment creation, poverty reduction, and adequate health care services.

Keywords: *poverty reduction, employment creation, health, small and medium enterprises, economic development*

Introduction

Today economic development has turned out to be a growing concern for many LDCs in the world. However as other continents continue to register sustainable economic growth and development, Africa is not only lagging but is trapped in the vicious cycle of borrowing and donor dependency syndrome which some critics point out as one of the causes of practically limiting development (Auren & Krassowska 2014). Africa has perpetually failed to focus its development efforts on the efficient optimum utilization of abundant natural resources that many countries are gifted with to turn it into wealth to boost their economies and people towards a high level of economic and social development. If developing countries are to achieve economic development, efforts have to be brought to supporting SMEs. However, there is no clear and universally acceptable description of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). According to the national archives of the United Kingdom, Bolton Committee 1971's report defines a "small firm as an independent business, managed by its owner or part-owners and having a small market share. Classification of SMEs is based on the number of employees, generally between 10 and 100, depending on the country in which the business is set up.

In Uganda, according to the Uganda Bureau of Statistics, SMEs can be broadly categorized according to three criteria; the number of employees, capital invested, and annual turnover. Upon this, small enterprises employ 5 to 49 people with total investment between 10 million but not exceeding 100 million and the medium enterprises employ between 50 and 100 people with total assets of Ugx: 100 but not exceeding 360 million. The Uganda Small Scale Industries Association (1998), offers a different definition altogether. To them, an SME is a business whose capital does not exceed US\$ 1,000 and employs not more than 50 persons.

SMEs consist of the driving force of industrial growth and development of the economy by ensuring diversification and growth of industrial production and the achievement of the basic objectives of developments. In some developing countries, SMEs are the central source of income generation, a breeding ground for entrepreneurs, and a provider of employment UNIDO Report (2003) as cited by Kehinde and Oladimeji (2016). Julius (2017) via the independent.co.ug, indicate that SMEs in Uganda make up over 70% of our economy and contribute above 20% of our GDP which is sizable. SMEs' work spans from service provision, selling of goods, information technology, agriculture and furniture making

among others. Acho & Abuh (2018) indicate that the contribution of small and medium scale enterprises to the development of any economy has been widely recognized because of their capacity in enhancing industrial output and human welfare

Karl (2005) summarizes economic development as "a process of creating and utilizing physical, human, financial, and social assets to generate improved and broadly shared economic well-being and quality of life for a community or region. Economic development was concerned with the expansion of people's entitlements and their corresponding capabilities, morbidity, nourishment, literacy, education, and other socio-economic indicators. (Todaro and Smith, 2011).

Furthermore, in Uganda, SMEs are regarded as an engine of economic growth, development and transformation through innovation and wealth creation (NDPII 2015/16-2019/20). The benefits of the small and medium enterprises in Uganda's economy cannot be overemphasized. SMEs dominate much of the country's economy, for example, 10% of the population are active in the manufacturing sector, 33 % in commerce, 49% in service and 8% in other fields (UIA, 2016), contributing close to 90% (2.5 million people) of the entire private sector employment, and 80% of manufactured products accounting for 20% of GDP (UBOS, 2016 and UIA, 2016). In addition, SMEs sector contributes 20% to Gross Domestic Product and it provides employment to over 1.5 million people which accounts for 90% of total non-farming private sector workers (UIA, 2008). However, several factors have been often cited out as constraints to the smooth performance and operation of SMEs thus leading to their failure in the due process and some even perform at less than optimal levels.

As highlighted above, SMEs have a great impact on the economic development as it employs the majority of the population, contributes to the country's revenue through tax collection as well as education and health sectors as most of the people involved in the sector use SMEs as sources for school fees and health support. This is inevitable as most of the SMEs are sole proprietors and looked at as an informal sector. Therefore, this research project is designed to study the influence of SMEs on the economic development of Kabarole District.

Statement of the problem

In Uganda, SMEs dominate much of the country's economy, as they employ the greatest population in the country. The existence of SMEs has been assumed to be beneficial to employment creation in particular and poverty eradication in general

(OECD, 2016) cited by (Adongo, 2019). But studies show how the economy is still lagging due to the increasing rates of unemployment, poverty, etc. UBOS on Labour Day (2019) indicated that the working-age population has increased to 19.1 million from 16.5 million persons in 2012/13. The national unemployment rate stands at 9% of the working-age population which increases the risk on the wellbeing of the citizens (UBOS, 2019) and this was worsened by the outbreak of the corona virus since business operations in the informal sector were neither registered nor protected by the state, have no registered interests or assets, and are vulnerable and excluded from governments impact mitigation programs for businesses, as well as social safety nets and protection accorded by formal labor contracts (Independent, 2016). Also, Uganda has over 50% of GDP (UBOS, 2014) which is attributed to the informal sector from 43% in 2002 to 80% of the labour force works in the informal economy and most of this is essential "underemployment" since most of the workers still don't earn enough to escape poverty. However much there has been a focus by National Development Plan (NDP III, 2020/21 – 2024/25) on the private sector SMEs inclusive, little is known on how best SMEs can be supported if the country is to achieve its vision of 2040. The key issues to SMEs growth have not been documented in the context of Uganda therefore this study aims to fill this research and knowledge gap on the influence of Small and Medium enterprises on economic development in the context of Kabarole District, a case study of Kiko T/C.

Purpose of the study.

To assess the influence of small and medium enterprises on the economic development in Kiko t/c, Kabarole District

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the determinants for SMEs growth
2. To find out the contributions of small and medium enterprises on economic development of Kabarole District.
3. To find out the challenges faced by the small and medium enterprises in Kabarole District

Justification of the study

Research has been conducted in the context of SMEs and economic development. However, the importance of SMEs towards job creation, a tool for poverty reduction, the mechanism to boost investment through processing and manufacturing have been studied but cases of unemployment,

poverty, and poor health still prevail in the economy. This is evident in the manner that SMEs are not given a high priority to address such cases

Conceptual review

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

and SMEs suffer challenges that limit growth. Therefore, this study intends to ascertain the influence of SMEs on economic development.

Source: (Storey, 1994; Prihatin, 2004; Rogoff et al., 2004; Hall, 1995) revised by the author(2021).

There are predicted variables of the SMEs' growth that were adopted by previous authors that include: motivation, education, experience, firm age and size, location, ownership, technology, marketing activities and policy, human resource, economic conditions, competition, strategic and financial management, infrastructure and external relationships (Storey, 1994; Prihatin, 2004; Rogoff et al., 2004; Hall, 1995). However, the research adopted few intervening variables (individual and organization factors) to SMEs growth. SMEs being the independent variable affected by the determinants and economic development as dependent variable described as employment creation, poverty reduction and health.

Literature Review

Theoretical review

Different theories have been developed to give a clear understanding of how businesses should grow and run however few lie in the context of SMEs. In this case, the theories concerning development will be discussed considering the role of SMEs. This review describes two theories and relating them to the topic of study.

2.1.1. Theory of Modernization

Modernization theory originated from the ideas of German sociologist Max Weber (1864–1920), which provided the basis for the modernization paradigm developed by Harvard sociologist Talcott Parsons (1902–1979). The theory looks at the internal factors of a country while assuming that with assistance, "traditional" countries can be brought to development in the same manner more developed countries have been. Modernization theory both attempts to identify the social variables that contribute to the social progress and development of societies and seeks to explain the process of social evolution. Modernization theory suggests that traditional societies will develop as they adopt more modern practices. The theory of modernization is focused not just on generating knowledge about whether a program is effective, but also on explaining what methods it uses to be effective. The theory draws attention to ways to modernize and how decision-making is influenced by the social and environmental factors in SMEs (Sulin, 2010). The theory emphasizes looking at new ways of doing work with a special focus on new technology that can be adopted. Theory of Modernization (ToM) is a specific type of methodology for planning, participation, and evaluation that is used in the philanthropy, not-for-profit and government sectors to promote social change. By way of modernization, a new approach that link between activities and long-term goals is understood (Dedan, 2013).

In relation to this study, in order to have modernization, there must be strong and committed leadership, especially in the difficult process of developing a 'vision' of a desirable future that the area and its residence must strive to achieve. There requires to be an effective consultation process of major stakeholders in the area among the community groups who must at the end support the planned investments and other important social and economic changes to take place. Small and medium enterprises are considered the best engine of development which require immediate attention if developing countries are to achieve their goals in

employment creation, poverty reduction and health care. However, they face a number of challenges for example inadequate capital to buy the stock and equipment to most of these industries. Securing loans from the financial and non-financial institutions takes time and in most cases was only on paper making them skip vital stages of growth.

2.1.2. Rostow's social economic theory

Rostow's social economic theory (1960) looks at the stages of growth. Rostow postulated a five stage model of development that will be able to apply to backward regions (Rostow, 1960). This model is vital in the sense that it is concerned with the idea that a country is able to develop economically by focusing on the resources that are in short supply in order to expand beyond local industries to reach global market and finance the country's further development to bring about economic development (Todaro and Smith, 2003).

In relation to this study, the theory advocated for a nation to focus and empower its people to rely on an activity where it has potential and help to stimulate economic development through aggressive investment to boost employment and reduce poverty in the state. Fifty percent of SMEs fight an uphill battle from the start and fail in the first five years due to a number of factors that affect the performance of SMEs for example business planning, access to credit and access to market information. This is a common scenario for Ugandan small and medium enterprises, as most of them 'never celebrate their first anniversary. Lack of skills is killing off most of the small scale enterprises in Uganda. For SMEs to survive there is need to carefully observe the stages of growth and how SMEs grow through the determinants.

2.2.0. Conceptual study

Generally, the term "business growth" is used to refer to various things, such as increase in total sales volume, increase in production capacity, increase in employment, increase in production volume, increase in the use of raw material and power. These factors indicate growth, but do not provide a specific meaning of growth. Business growth is typically defined and measured using absolute or relative changes in sales, assets, employment, productivity, profits and profit margins. This study is in support of the view by Delmar, Davidson and Gartner (2003) who posited that various scholars use growth indicators such as assets, market share, physical output and profits to measure business performance. Yet they argued these indicators are usually not used as sales and employment, because their applicability is limited;

therefore this project thought the need to study smes determinants (individual and organisation factors) and sme growth reflected in employment and sales maximisation

2.2.1.0. Individual factors as a determinant of SMEs growth

2.2.1.1. Education

2.2.1.1.1. Education and training.

Education is a teaching and learning system aiming to socialize individuals and maximize their development. Though it may be commonly linked to knowledge, these two terms should not be confused. Education is related to moral rules, while knowledge is broader than that (Souza 2020). Despite being linked to moral rules; it doesn't represent them in itself. Therefore, education is considered an extensive system, with different methods, procedures and tools. Education is the most vital of all resources. It is widely recognized that formal education positively impacts entrepreneur's decisions when it comes to increasing business growth opportunities (Dunkelberg and Cooper, 1982; Cooper et al., 1994). Owner or managers who possess education may be able to cope with problems and consequently be more successful (Hall and Wahab, 2007) or foster business growth (Honjo, 2004). This has been asserted by Cooper et al. (1994) and Almus (2002) that years of schooling or university studies have impacted business growth. In addition, education provides knowledge that may help overcome financial constraints (Evans and Leighton, 1989). Moreover, the firms' owner or managers who have better education level are more efficient in their work and will tend to build their character and enhance the skills (Souitaris et al., 2007). The formal education may provide entrepreneurs with a greater capacity to learn individual capabilities to process new information, new production and product designs, specific technical knowledge related to firm expansion and increase owners' flexibility (Parker et al., 2003). Additionally, more educated entrepreneurs have the necessary dedication, discipline, motivation and self-confidence to attain higher growth rates in their businesses (Cooper et al., 1994). Training is considered as a subdivision of education. When managers undergo training, the business could potentially have greater assets and sales revenue (Kessy and Temu, 2010) whereby in the training sessions, the managers add certain/new skills or become more efficient in those skills, which they already have. Other positive impacts of the training such as the capability of completing challenging tasks, having control over one's own job, moving upwards in terms of the enterprise activities; creating more opportunities for enterprises (Singh and Belwal, 2008; Apospori et al., 2005); acquiring

knowledge on better management techniques and developing business network commercial activities (Roomi et al., 2009). The lack of training was a major factor impeding the growth of SMEs in developing countries (Taiwo et al., 2012). Most training is formal in nature, however, the training differs from education slightly in terms of the duration and specialized skills acquisition. Training is also related to the motivations factors of employees for growth, encourage and it can change their behaviors in their working places (Singh and Belwal, 2008), which may affect the earnings (Dearden et al., 2000) and productivity of firms (Winkelman, 1994). Shariff and Peaou (2008) asserted that any business processes will only succeed if employees are adequately equipped with skills and motivation

2.2.1.2. Work experience

Work experience is another relevant dimension of human capital that may have an impact on firm's growth (Bosma et al., 2004). Work experience gives entrepreneurs specific knowledge and managerial capabilities, which can help to develop more successful strategies leading to higher growth rates (Lazear, 2005). The experience is the best teacher in learning processes, thus, with sufficient previous experiences, entrepreneurs would not repeat any mistakes that they had committed before. Moreover, Other studies by Schutjens and Wever (2000) and Friar and Meyer (2003), found a positive relationship, Zimmer and Scarborough (2006) noted that the main reason behind the business failure is due to the absence of experiences, especially on the managerial aspect managers' business experience and firm's growth. All of these indicate that the experience is needed in driving business into a success. Some authors disagreed and stated that the previous labor market experience has a negative correlation to firms' growth (Westhead and Cowling, 1995; Brüderl and Preisendörfer, 2000). However, the managerial experience is wider in scope and more complex than labor market experience, and many authors agreed with its positive relationship.

2.2.2.0. Organisationa factors as a determinant of SMEs growth

2.2.2.1. Firm's strategy

Schendel & Hatten (1972) defined strategy as the basic goals and objectives of the organization, the major programs of action chosen to reach these goals and objectives, and the major pattern of resource allocation used to relate the organization to its environment. Strategy provides both direction and cohesion to the enterprise and is composed of several steps: strategic profile, strategic forecast, resource audit, strategic

alternatives explored, tests for consistency and, finally, strategic choice. (Ackerman & Rosenblum, 1973). Beaver (2002) defined strategy as the action that an organization takes to pursue its business objectives. Beaver pointed out that strategy drives performance, hence an effective strategy should result in a good performance. He added that an organization's strategy is a multifaceted concept, which can be viewed from a number of perspectives, depending on which aspects of its actions are of interest.

Roper (1997) proposed that strategies that are to be changed over time might be positive for performance development but they need to be benchmarked continuously in achieving the best practices. A new venture's success or failure depends almost totally on the strategic initiatives taken by the firms. Previous investigations show the relationship between new venture strategies and firm growth such as financing (Tsai and Li, 2007). However, other studies suggest no relationship between strategy and growth (Campbell-Hunt, 2000). Therefore, building an effective firm's strategy is central to any firm as it enables it to achieve and maintain a competitive advantage. Hence, in order to survive, firms require a combination of various strategies that are appropriate for rapid environmental changes. In the literature on strategy, researchers have used various variables to represent a firm's strategic activities that are referred to as strategic orientations (Weinzimmer, Robin, & Michel, 2012). However, there are limited studies in Uganda regarding SMEs growth particularly Kabarole district.

2.2.3.0. Contribution of SMEs on economic development

The contribution of SMEs has been view by different scholar in many ways i.e. a tool to boost the country's GDP, job creation, poverty reduction, mechanism to boost investment through processing and manufacturing, improving education standards, health, among others. But this study is intended to find out the contributions of SMEs on economic development focusing on employment creation, poverty reduction and health care services.

2.2.3.1. SMEs and employment creation

Adongo (2019) in her study "the impact of small and medium enterprises on employment creation in Uganda with specific reference to Lira Municipality" indicated that majority (74.6%) of the respondents are employed in different categories of SMEs, and 25.4% of the respondents are not employed in any SME. This implies that SMEs have contributed to creating employment to people in Lira Municipality.

SMEs create job opportunities across geographic areas and sectors, employing broad segments of the labour force, including low-skilled workers, and providing opportunities for skills development. They also help support their employees' access to health care and social services. SMEs that generate jobs and value added are therefore an important channel for inclusion and poverty reduction, especially but not exclusively in emerging and low-income economies. In this regard, upgrading productivity in a large population of small businesses, including in traditional segments and the informal economy, can help governments achieve both economic growth and social inclusion objectives, including escaping from low productivity traps and improving the quality of jobs for low-skilled workers (OECD, 2017).

Erdirin, and Ozkaya (2020) attribute that great unemployment crisis in the 1980s led policymakers to concentrate on small and medium-sized enterprises in the member countries. It was thought that large enterprises' production, employment, and investment problems could be solved by taking advantage of SMEs. SMEs were handled with sensitivity in all economic arrangements, incentive policies and legislative implementations made after 1990.

According to the report by Dr Sarwar Hobohm(not shown) about small and medium sized enterprises in economic development, through a UNIDO experience show clearly the contribution of SMEs as being more labour intensive and tend to lead to a more equitable distribution of income than large enterprises. They play an important role in generating employment and thus alleviating poverty, often providing employment opportunities at a reasonable rates of remuneration to workers from poor household and women who have few alternative sources of income. Acho & Abuh A, (2018) in there study, Assessment of the contributions of small scale enterprises to the development of the Nigerian economy found out that there is no doubt that small scale businesses are essential for rapid and sustained economic growth and development because they create employment, enhance capacity building for manpower and skills development, promote growth, and facilitate industrial development among others. Several efforts have been made by successive governments to promote SSBs amidst the vast availability of human and materials resources. These efforts have made small scale businesses to contribute significantly to the development of the Nigerian economy. In addition, SMEs contribute to a more efficient allocation of resources in developing

countries, they tend to adopt a labour intensive production method and thus more accurately reflect the resource endowments in developing countries where labour is plentiful and capital is scarce.

Anyanwu (2003) Opined that SMEs enhance employment generation in a place since unemployed youths and graduates can easily engage in skills on their own. Small and medium enterprises generate more employment opportunities on the aggregate than giant industries. Many people in this country depend on self-employment for sustenance. Many others including their relations are provided employment in these enterprises directly and indirectly.

2.2.3.2. SMEs and Poverty Reduction

Poverty measured by the proportion of population living below the poverty line, is observed to be declining over time in Uganda. The percentage of the poor people living below the poverty line fell from 56% in 1992 to 44% in 1997 and 35% in 2000 but rose to 38% in 2002 (Germina Ssemogere 2005). Poverty in Uganda is mainly urban slum and rural phenomenon, with 96% of the poor living in rural areas in 2000. To reduce the rural-urban income gap (inequality), the poverty eradication action plan (PEAP) emphasis among other things the strategic improvement of access to credit by the poor through the savings and credit cooperatives. The most vulnerable categories in the community are women and girls. Through lack of education and jobs, there is temptation for those between 12 and 25 years of yield to commercial sex. This is a critical interface on which sensitization and information education and communication should focus (Ssengondo et al. 2001).

Mohammad et al. (2015) ascertained that the contribution of SMEs in eradicating poverty depend on individuals' or a group of people that have certain factors. These factors include innovativeness, family background, government support programs, and training or education. Additionally, others factors are individual entrepreneurial characteristics, an increase in women participation in entrepreneurship, youth empowerment and robust policies. Robust policies and collaborations, especially among government-university-industry stimulate employment and job creation that can results into reduction in poverty. Although governments in developing economies recognize the potential of SMEs in economic growth and poverty reduction enabling policies and programmes have not been provided for their effective performance.

Diagne and Zeller (2001) argues that lack of adequate access to credit for the poor may have negative consequences for various household level outcomes including technology adoption, SMEs profitability, food security, nutrition, health and overall welfare. Access to credit therefore affects welfare outcomes by alleviating the capital constraints on SMEs, hence enabling poor entrepreneurs with little or no savings to acquire capital. This reduces the opportunity costs of capital intensive assets relative to family labour, thus encouraging the adoption of labour-saving, higher-yielding technologies and therefore increasing capital and SMEs profitability.

Rhynne and Otero (1992) argued that financially sustainable SMEs with outreach have a greater likelihood of having a positive impact on poverty alleviation because they guarantee sustainable access to credit by the poor. Outreach is the number of clients served by SMES. Financial sustainability on the other hand measures the extent to which the SMES covers its operational and financial costs from internally generated revenues (interests and commissions). SMEs with higher repayment rates are more likely to be financially sustainable.

Ali (2013) highlighted the SMEs and poverty in Pakistan. According to him, SMEs have a significant contribution to the economic development, poverty alleviation and employment creation in the economy. The author has used a time series data from 1972 to 2008 for investigating the role of the SME sector in poverty alleviation in Pakistan. The results confirmed a strong impact of SME growth on poverty alleviating in the country. He advised that economic policymakers have to focus on the establishment of proper financial markets to control financial constraints, faced by the SME sector in the country. The simplification of a lending procedure, the implementation of credit rights, and a decrease in credit costs would be supportive for the establishment of a robust SME area in Pakistan.

2.2.3.3. SMEs and Health

According to the report of Banyan global "Uganda's private health sector: opportunities for growth" through USAID in 2015 shows that the majority of the private health sector (76%) is composed of facilities providing outpatient services to address common diseases like malaria along with somewhat larger clinics that offer delivery and laboratory services. Twelve percent of the sector are Health Centre IV facilities, operating as 'mini hospitals' with inpatient care and surgical capabilities. Most private clinics tend to cluster

around urban areas resulting in limited rural healthcare coverage. A wide variety of services are offered through Uganda's private health clinics ranging from obstetrics and gynecology, family planning, TB treatment, child health immunizations, sexually transmitted infection (STI) treatments, and safe male circumcisions. Based on interviews with private health clinic staff, malaria prevention and treatment, HIV/AIDS counselling/testing, and general health education are the most commonly offered services.

Gaps in public health services have often been filled by non-profit organizations and charities (BBC, 2017). Despite the existence of healthcare systems, non-profit organizations such as in the area of cancer have propped up care for decades, plugging gaps in home care, travel costs, research funding and palliative care, as well as helping patients navigate the complexities of the health system itself (Agrawal et al. 2015)

McCann and Ortega (2016) argue that in all the talk about EU innovation, one crucial area is often overlooked in the policy arena for health and care systems and that is the role of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The healthcare sector encompasses several categories of interest to present and future SMEs deciding whether to enter the healthcare services and product market. This includes medical equipment, instruments and services as well as biotechnology, diagnostic laboratories and substances, primary prevention sensors (i.e. wearable health systems based on wireless body sensor networks) plus medicine development and delivery. With respect to innovative medical devices in the personalized medicine era, the possibilities are huge in diagnosis, therapy and business e.g. from diagnostics, therapy, companion diagnostics and monitoring to commodities suitable to more general healthcare provision (Denis Horgan et al. 2018). Investment in SMEs in the healthcare arena can have the same impact with the development of innovative healthcare services and products that will impact on citizens' quality of life (European Commission, 2018) cited by Denis Horgan et al. (2018).

Healthcare is a unique area for innovation, and often health means wealth whether that be driving economic growth and creating jobs or reducing costs across increasingly cash-strapped healthcare systems dealing with ageing populations and the attendant increases in co-morbidities and chronic diseases (Denis Horgan et al. 2018).

In a 2014 survey of healthcare businesses in Uganda, 78% noted that their major constraint to running operations was lack of financing, specifically to

purchase new equipment and for working capital needs. (Banyan global "USAID" 2014 survey)

This is evident that if Uganda is to achieve sustainable health care services much attention has to be devoted to SMEs due to the fact that they are easily accessible than large health facilities. This was due to the high cost require by the large firms that is not convenient to the rural poor people.

2.3. Challenges faced by SMEs in their operations

Although much efforts are being invested in order to create a conducive business environment for the growth of newly formed and development of existing SMEs, many of them shut down during the first years of existence due to a number of factors, both internal and external nature. Different studies have been conducted in the field of obstacles/limitation and/or challenges faced by SMEs. Findings have shown managerial skills, access to credit, taxation policies, information opaqueness, competition, inadequate capital, among others have been identified as key bottlenecks to SMEs. This study was designed to find out if managerial skills and access to credit as key challenges faced by SMEs in their operation in the context of Kiko town council.

2.3.1. Managerial skills

Managerial skills according to George & Jones (2001) refer to the ability of a manager (of a small-scale enterprise) to perform managerial tasks and/or roles effectively and efficiently. Boden & Nucci (2000) defined managerial skills as the ability of an entrepreneur to execute managerial roles, which according to them include marketing, financial management, book keeping and supervision. Ihua (2009) attribute that despite SMEs major role in economic empowerment and development, SMEs encounter numerous constraints and challenges. For instance, the country does not have a policy governing their operation. Furthermore, he described lack of necessary skills and competencies to enable them to effectively carry out the various SME activities, while there are various essential functional activities required for operating any type of business: accounting, legal, management, marketing, financing and international business management skills. Big businesses rely on specialists' knowledge which small businesses, usually, cannot afford. As a result, small business owners perform most of those functions. Doing all these activities may be an impediment to the growth and development of the business and may deter entrepreneurship in that SMEs may not have all the necessary competencies to hold out the wide

selection of activities. The situation is expected to be worse in a globalized context, where most businesses have to internationalize their business corporations and have to deal with intensified competition.

Joshua Mutambi (2013) in his survey on Stimulating Industrial Development in Uganda through Open Innovation Incubators brings it out that though SMEs are the prime source of new jobs and play a crucial role in income generation as well as in industrialization processes, smallest businesses fail within their early stages of operation mainly due to under-capitalization and/or lack of proper management and business skills.

According to Sharmilee and Muhammad (2016) in their paper factors affecting the performance of small and medium enterprises in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. Managerial competency and skills were identified. The study revealed that more than half (59.16%) of the respondents viewed managerial competency and skills shortage as a factor that affects the performance of the business.

Hisrich & Drnovsek (2002) in their study, it was found that managerial competencies positively impact on the performance of SMEs and further, pointed out by Martin & Staines (2008) SME failure is a result of lack of managerial experience. The results indicated that SME owners/managers lack prior experience in managing this sort of business (31.34%) and lack experience in small business management (30.43%). If SMEs are to survive, they need to obtain the required skill.

In Uganda, a study by Everest (2015) found out that there is a strong interdependence between human capital, social capital and financial capital. Technical and management skills will determine the amount of social and financial capital generated for the SMEs. This is because human capital provides management skills (Kasekende & Opondo, 2003; Tusubira & Nabeta, 2013) As such, SMEs lack good quality human capital which also means limited marketing and financial planning, lack of good business plans; poor business records and deficient corporate governance (Apire, 2003, UNEP, 2007). In addition, due to their small size, a simple management mistake is likely to lead to collapse of SMEs hence no opportunity to learn from its past mistakes (Bowen, Morara & Mureithi, 2009). In his policy framework, improving managerial skills was necessary if SMEs are to achieve growth.

A study conducted by Kibuuka (2015) about managerial skills and the success of small scale enterprises showed moderate extent of managerial skills in terms of conceptual, human and technical

skills; less successful internally and more successful externally; the extent of managerial skills and success differed significantly according to gender, education level, business form and years in business; the extent of managerial skills possessed was positively and significantly correlated with all aspects of internal and external success; conceptual and technical skills significantly depicted small-scale entrepreneurs' success. Thus, technical and conceptual skills needed to be more promoted through entrepreneurial and business skills in universities; education of small-scale entrepreneurs on formation of joint ventures and ongoing training programs for skills formation and development.

Nakiyinji (2010) study results revealed that there was a significant positive relationship between managerial competencies and success of businesses. This implies that existence of managerial competencies in the business will result into business success and lack of managerial competencies results into failure of the business. She further stated that the linkage between independence, capacity building, networking, enterprising, commitment and resilience were observed to be positively significant to business success. This is because they describe the skills and attributes the staff need to meet future challenges, help clarify expectations and provide a sound basis for consistent and objective performance standards by creating a shared language about what is needed and expected in an organization.

2.3.2. Access to credit

In the study by Ackah and Vuvor (2011) The Challenges faced by Small & Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Obtaining Credit in Ghana, show that 60% representing 41 of the total respondents of 68 ranked lack of collateral because the major factor preventing them from accessing loans from the financial institutions. 15 or 22% ranked small equity base as factor affecting their access to credit. Lack of experienced management was the opinion of 7 or 10% of the respondents with 4% thinking that other factors such as the inability to provide audited financial statement are preventing them from accessing credit with 3% relating their inability to access credit to default on previous loan. Again aside from the collateral issues and other factors as indicated above, which makes it very difficult for SMEs to access the utmost amount needed for various expansion projects, the interest rates charges on the loan facilities by the various banks are outrageous and also unattractive for most SMEs to access these credits. Almost all the respondents expressed an opinion on the level

of interest rates charged by financial institutions on facilities received, to be extremely high while others also say the rates are just high. In addition, the level of interest rates charges on loans from the bank and non-bank financial institutions, 48 out of the 68 responses received from participants saw the interest rates on loans to be extremely high. This represented 71% of the total responses. 18 or 26% of the entire respondent think the rates are high with just 3% saying the rates are manageable. The extremely high interest rate group numbering about 48 out of the total respondents of 68 pays interest between 31% and 40% per annum. 26% of the respondents, which indicated that the rates charged by the financial institution are high, also pay interest of 21% to 30% per annum, with just 3%, which we will term the “fortunate” ones servicing their loans at an interest of less than 20% per annum. This makes their businesses unprofitable because the profits made are eroded by the large finance cost.

Sharmilee and Muhammad (2016) in their study showed that the main source of funding is equity (34.33%) followed by short term debt (31.34%). Accessibility to finance may be a major factor affecting the expansion and success of SMEs, which may be attributed to several factors (Haron et al., 2013). More than two-thirds (72%) of the SME owner/manager believe that access to finance may be a major challenge affecting the expansion of business.

In South Africa, access to finance has been identified as the major constraint, reducing the survival and growth of start-up SMEs (Mazanai & Fatoki, 2012). In addition, researchers reported that access to finance may be a struggle for SMEs in South Africa and particularly for firms in emerging economies (Berger & Udell, 2006). In addition, the results of the study on difficulties in accessing finance showed that only half the SME owners/managers (52.24%) experience difficulties in accessing finance.

Acho & Abuh A, (2018) concluded that, in spite of government policies aimed at providing financial and technical support for the promotion of small business enterprises in Nigeria, they have performed less satisfactorily largely because of operational bottlenecks including lack of depth of the financial system, inadequate infrastructural facilities, poor management practices and low entrepreneurial skills to mention but a few. Banks which are supposed to provide adequate credit facilities in compliance to government policies, usually place exorbitant interest rate alongside huge collateral securities that scare away investor

Locally a study by Nakiyinjji (2010) revealed that Access to credit had a positive correlation with business success of the SMEs’ in Uganda. This may be explained by the short time the SMEs take to access the loans and are able to acquire reliable needs and assets that they need from such credit hence reflecting firm success. The security that is also required to access the credit being favourable to SMEs boosts their borrowing from the money lending institutions and this in turn improves on the performance of the SMEs. The study further revealed that loan amounts offered by the banks encouraged more SMEs’ to access credit in various forms from the commercial banks and hence better performance.

2.4. Research gap

Besides, most studies are observed to have studied SMEs such as kessy & temu 2010, singh & belwal 2008, sheriff & peaou 2008 among others, the scope in such studies have been studied is limited in Uganda. They have not clearly studied the SMEs in detail to help policy makers in supporting SMEs if economic development is to be achieved. Thus necessitating this study so as to address this gap which opted to study SMEs growth, contributions and challenges at ago. In addition, some studies have only considered small samples which made their conclusions to be underrated, therefore this study considered a sample relative huge number of SMEs.

Methodology

Introduction

This chapter presents a strategy that was utilized in this study. The chapter describes the research design, area of study, study population, sample size determination, procedure for data collection, data collection instruments, data analysis techniques, validity and reliability, limitations of the study and ethical consideration.

Research design

The study adopted a cross sectional survey design since it permits the collection of information from a sample of a predetermined population. Cross sectional design is best suited to studies aimed at finding out the prevalence of a phenomenon, attitude or issue and is useful in obtaining an overall picture as it stands at the time of the study about the phenomenon (Kumar, 2005). The cases used were SMEs such as those in Agriculture, Hotel and Catering Services, Real Estate and Construction, General merchandise trade, Petroleum products trade, Fabrication and Service Provision within Kiko t/c. Firstly, Kiko T/C was selected given a number of SMEs operating in this area consisting of different categories. Secondly, among the several town councils of Kabarole District, Kiko T/C have the largest number of SMEs and therefore it was easy to locate the businesses for the survey. The outcomes from this location were a true representation for other councils and generally other SMEs operating in urban centre of Kabarole District. The SMEs businesses include carpentry, metal works, retail businesses, food and beverages, textiles, stationary among others. The study employed structured and unstructured questionnaires to gather information by kobo collect and later transfer to SPSS for further analysis.

Area of study

The research will be conducted in the town councils of Kabarole District, specifically aiming at Kiko T/C for the greater number of SMEs than other town councils.

Study population.

This study covered the area of kiko t/c in Kabarole District. According to Babbie and Mouton (2006), the population for a study is that group (usually of people) about whom we want to draw conclusions. The researcher's survey populations will be the owners/managers of small and medium enterprises dealing in bakery, wood work, grain milling, restaurants and food processing, garages for motorcars and motorcycles, retail and wholesale

trade, clinics, metal fabrication, furniture assembling, and transport services and some of the employees in SMES. Through survey, most SMEs were not register and it was therefore very hard to know the exact number of SMEs in Kiko. However, through observation, SMEs in Kiko are over 150.

Sample size determination

The sample size was obtained using Cochran's formula since the study involved the use sampling units obtained from different groupings which are the divisions.

$$n = Z^2P(1-P)/d^2$$

Where n= required sample size

Z =the statistical certainty chosen as 90% confidence level

P = Target population

1-P = population with unwanted characteristics

d = precision desired/margin of error

The researcher used a response rate of 50% because this is what is normally used by researchers whenever one hasn't used a response rate from previous studies. The 90% confidence level (error of 10%). This was used in order to minimize the sample size due to financial and time constraints. Therefore; given n=? ,

$$Z= 1.64(90\%), P= 50\%, 1-P=1-50\%, d= 0.1$$

From the formula $n= 1.642 *0.5(1-0.5)/0.12 = 67.24\%$

$$=75*(67.24/100)$$

$$= 50 \text{ respondents}$$

Therefore, the sample size for the respondents of this study was 50 respondents.

The procedure for data collection

Upon obtaining an approval of the research proposal by the university supervisor, the researcher will obtain consent of the respondents to collect data from participants (SMEs) and other stake holders in Kabarole District. The researcher will rely on voluntary participation of respondents, ensure informed consent to the respondents and assure them of confidentiality of their responses. Respondents will be assured that the data provided will be used for purposes of this study only. More information relating to the topic of study will be got through observation during the process of data collection.

Data collecting instruments

Data collection entails gaining permissions, developing means for recording information and anticipating ethical issues (Creswell 2013). This area describes the instruments that the researcher used in collecting data in a more reliable, convenient and effective manner to the research objectives and the researcher's resources.

Questionnaire

The researcher used the questionnaire survey as the key data collection method. Obtaining systematic information from small and medium enterprises is a major challenge for researchers because of lack and updated contact information. Past experience has showed that SMEs are reluctant to respond to hard copy questionnaire and mail survey because of time constraints by the owners and also in their understanding and interpretation of the terminology in the questionnaire. A structured and unstructured questionnaire was designed on paper to suit the objectives of the study and later transformed to kobo tool box that operates hand in hand with the kobo collect. Kobo collect is phone application that is used to collect data and to help the researcher collect data and verbally explain the questions with a standard protocol. Later the data will be stored on the kobo tool box server for analysis and later transferred to SPSS and excel analyzer for further analysis. The questionnaire was designed with different sections, section A covering about the background information of the respondent like gender, age group, level of education, marital status and the position at the business. The other sections were set to cater for the objectives of the study.

Observation

This study adopted the use of observation method sorely for purposes of time constraint. The researcher used his skills in finding out the real image of business in relation to the topic of study in the process of collecting data.

Data Analysis

Data analysis may be described as a process of inspecting, cleansing, transforming and modeling data with the goal of discovering useful information, informing conclusion and supporting decision-making. Statistician John Tukey defined data analysis in 1961 as: "Procedures for analyzing data, techniques for interpreting the results of such procedures, ways of designing the gathering of knowledge to make its analysis easier, more precise or more accurate, and every one the machinery and results of (mathematical) statistics which apply to analyzing data. This study therefore employed both

quantitative and qualitative data analysis techniques

Quantitative data analysis

Quantitative data was collected using structured questions on the kobo tool box platform. Then the information was entered using a computer and analyzed using SPSS and excel analyzer. Quantitative analysis was done using descriptive statistics of frequencies, mean, median, mode and percentages. Ranks were also undertaken to establish a relationship between items basing of frequency of occurrences. However, of these methods were used to draw up conclusive ideas through graphs, pie-charts among others. Descriptive statistics was in sort of frequency tabulations.

Qualitative data analysis

The responses from unstructured questions on the questionnaire were edited and data organized and aggregated consistent with themes for meaningful interpretation in line with the objectives of the study. The qualitative data was analyzed by listing down the respondents' views under each question category by objective. Similar views presented by quite one respondent were organized into categories consistent with themes. This is often thematic analysis which is consistent with (Bamberger et al., 2006) involves viewing data several times, identifying patterns and themes and reorganizing data i.e. coding data consistent with themes identified

Validity and Reliability

Heale & Twycross (2015) defined validity as the extent to which an idea is accurately measured during a quantitative study, Reliability concerns the extent to which a measurement of a phenomenon provides stable and consist result. Reliability is additionally concerned with repeatability. For instance, a scale or test is claimed to be reliable if repeat measurement made by it under constant conditions will give the same result. Therefore, the results which will be presented during this scientific research are going to be valid and reliable to the extent of due analysis and consistency is formed on the data.

Ethical considerations

During this study, the researcher adhered to moral issues/norms in research because they enhance the aim of research which incorporates the dissemination of data, reporting or saying the reality and eventually the necessity to counteract errors. Participants' consent will be obtained through better introduction of the researcher to

respondents/superiors who clearly specified what the research involved, including clearly laid down procedures and explain the ways during which their confidentiality are going to be assured. The profile of the respondents is going to be withheld to make sure confidentiality of their personal information and also informed that data won't be shared but are going to be used for the aim of this study.

Limitations of the study.

The study was interesting within the initial stage however the researcher faced some identical limitations to other previous researchers within the field of finding the empirical evidence to the matter in any quite research. However much this being the primary scientific research to conduct, the researcher faced other constraints not only limited to resources like time, finance and professional individuals in research but also limited information on international information platforms (internet) about SMEs within the context of Kabarole district that might have guided the researcher.

Conclusion

The researcher used a cross-sectional study design during this study i.e. qualitative and quantitative data analysis. A sample size of 50 SMEs was selected from a population of over 150 SMEs working within the Kiko t/c of Kabarole District. The main data collection tool was a questionnaire which had both structured and unstructured questions that was designed through kobo tool box and data collected by kobo collect. Quantitative techniques were wont to analyze responses from structured questions, while qualitative methods were wont to analyze/summarise findings from observations and unstructured questions in the questionnaire. Chapter four presents the results, analysis and evaluation of findings.

Results, Conclusions & Recommendations

Determinants of SMEs

The following are tables represent data from some of the questions in line with the determinants of SMEs

Education

Response	Frequency	Percent
No	15	31.3
Yes	33	68.8
Total	48	100.0

Sales of SMEs operated by educated people

Response	N	M	S.D
SMEs operated by educated people sale more than those without an educated people	48	4.08	1.164

Experience and sales

Response	Frequency	Percent
No	15	33.3
Yes	32	67
Total	47	97.9

Strategy ownership

Response	Frequency	Percent
No	36	75
Yes	12	25
Total	48	100

The study found out that the small and medium enterprises employed educated people (66.8%) and had an impact on the business growth through and majority of the respondents continued to agree that small and medium enterprises that were operated by educated people made a lot of sales ($M=4.08$, $SD=1.164$) than those with uneducated people due to the adverse knowledge educated possess that is necessary in regard to decision making. On the years of experience, the study found out that most of the respondents had ran the enterprise for some good number of years which implied that they had enough experience in regard to the business they operate and the findings were supported by Lazear (2005). The study also found out that people with experience contributed a lot on sales increase in their respective enterprises (67%).

On the firm's strategy, the study also found out that majority of small and medium enterprises had no strategies (75%) that they follow in their operation and it was also found out that those business that had a strategy sold more than those without.

Contributions of SMEs on economic development

The following are tables represent data from some of the questions in line with the contribution of SMEs

SMEs and employment creation

Response	Frequency	Percent
No	39	81.2
Yes	9	18.8
Total	48	100

SMEs and poverty reduction

Response	N	M	S.D.
Do you think currently SMEs have contributed to poverty reduction in Kiko t/c	48	4.12	1.347

SMEs and affordable health care accessibility

Response	N	M	S.D.
We get health care services from clinics at cheaper cost compared to big hospitals	48	3.73	1.554

Health sector in Kiko

The study found out that SMEs have great contributed to employment creation (81.2%) in Kiko t/c through casual and office work and some even employed their family members. Also the findings show that the people involved in the running SMEs were not sure where their business will greatly contribute to employment creation in the future. On poverty reduction, the study found out that poverty is still prevailing in Kiko, however the cause for poverty increase was backed up by a report by UBOS on the labour day (2019), but however the study also found out that SMEs have greatly contributed to poverty reduction ($M=4.12$, $SD=1.347$) in Kiko t/c. the

findings on the health care in Kiko show that people continue to get cheaper services(56%) from small and medium enterprises operating as clinics than the big hospitals, and they continued to agree that health sector in Kiko is good however variance between those who said yes or no is very small to conclude that the health sector in Kiko is good.

Challenges faced by small and medium enterprises in Kiko t/c

The following are tables represent data from some of the questions in line with the contribution of SMEs

Access to credit

Response	Frequency	Percent
No	29	60.4
Yes	19	39.6
Total	48	100

Limitations to accessing credit

Response	Frequency	Percent
Interest rates	16	33.3
Lack of collateral	22	45.8
Not registered	6	12.5
Have no bank a/c	4	8.3
Total	47	97.9

Managerial skills

Response	N	M	S.D
The firm/business has a good management	47	3.70	1.413
The business employs educated people with managerial skills	47	3.73	1.427

Training of employees

The study found out that most of the SMEs do not access credit (60.4%) and they attributed that the cause was greatly linked to lack of collateral security (45.8%) and high interest rates (33.3%). The findings were not in line with Acho and Abuh A in 2018. The findings later found out that these SMEs had a strong management ($M=3.70$, $SD=1.413$) and they argued that SMEs employed educated people ($M=3.73$, $SD=1.427$), but this was unsatisfactory about the

extent to which the management was good if they don't train employees (60%) to increase efficiency of their employees. The study also found out that access to credit and lack of managerial skills evidenced in failure to train employees were not only the major challenges to SMEs in Kiko but also limited capital, narrow customer base, poor infrastructure specifically roads and high taxes were other challenges faced by small and medium enterprises in Kiko.

Conclusions

The research project found out that majority SMEs employed more males than females who were educated to level of tertiary/university level. SMEs with educated people greatly had an impact on the business sales. Managers and/or owners had experience their respective business which aided to sale more however most of the business didn't have strategies to guide their operation which would have a negative impact on the growth of the business.

On the contribution of SMEs on employment creation, they have shown a great impact in Kiko through casual and office work however, unemployment in Kiko was high due to the growing population and some SMEs were not sure if they could employ more people. the poverty levels seemed to be covered up through the casual work however the number of SMEs could not unleash that problem due population growth and the initiation of SMEs operating as clinics contributed to the health sector in Kiko.

The great contribution of these SMEs on economic development was however greatly limited by access to credit and lack of training that imposed doubt on the managerial competence. Other challenges like limited capital, narrow customer base, poor infrastructure and high taxes that drained their profits were other challenges that were cited.

Recommendations

Since it was evidenced in the study that unemployment and poverty still had room Kiko, the policy makers should either support the local entrepreneurs to boost employment creation as a result poverty rates will reduce.

The health sector in Kiko has to be improved due to the growing population so as to maintain a healthy economy.

From the study, findings showed that SMEs do not train and had no strategies to provide an effective platform for management to run the business, a lot of effort by SMEs has to be brought to training and strategy formulation in order to aid the managers and/or owners.

Financial providers have to in all matters possible design measure to assist small and medium enterprises

to raise finance if the goal of economic development is to be achieved at all levels through employment

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Study questionnaire

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR OWNERS OF SMEs AND SUPERVISORS/MANAGERS

Dear Respondent,

I am Tumwesigye Robert a student at Uganda Pentecostal University undertaking a Degree in Business Administration. In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of a degree in Business Administration, I am undertaking a research titled “the influence of small and medium enterprise on the economic development”. The questionnaire provides a set of structured questions seeking responses on the topic as provided. Please be as objective as possible in responding to the questions asked by the enumerator. All responses provided will remain confidential; and will be used purely for academic purposes.

SECTION A: Background Information (Tick Where Applicable)

1. Sex of respondents

Sex	Tick	Measure
Male		1
Female		2

2. Age groups of respondents

Age group	Tick	Measure
15-25		1
26-32		2
33-41		3
41 and above		4

3. Highest level of education

Level of education	Tick	Measure
Primary		1
Secondary		2
Tertiary/ University		3
Never		4

4. Respondents Marital Status

Marital status	Tick	Measure
Single		1
Married		2
Divorced		3
Widow		4
Rather not to say		5

SECTION B: SMEs and economic development (Tick Where Applicable)

Objective 1. Determinants for SMEs growth?

2.0 Education

2.1 Educated people have an impact of a business growth?

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

2.2 SMEs operated by educated people sale more than those with uneducated people?

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Strongly agree		1
b)	Agree		2
c)	Disagree		3
d)	Strongly disagree		4

3.0. Work experience

3.1 How long have you been running this enterprise (years)

Years	
-------	--

3.2. Do u you think experience has helped increase you sales and number of employees?

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

4.0. Firm’s strategy

4.1. Do you have a strategy that your business follows?

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

4.2. Firms with strategies sale more than those without.

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Strongly agree		1
b)	Agree		2
c)	Disagree		3
d)	Strongly disagree		4

Objective 2. What are the contributions of small and medium enterprises on economic development in Kabarole District?

5.0. Employment creation

5.1. There is high unemployment in Kiko t/c

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

5.2. Small and medium enterprise have contributed to employment creation in Kiko t/c

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

5.3.
We

expect SMEs to employ more people in Kiko t/c in the nearby future

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Strongly agree		1
b)	Agree		2
c)	Disagree		3
d)	Strongly disagree		4

6.0. Poverty reduction

6.1. How do you rate poverty in Kiko t/c in the last five (5) years?

a)	High	
b)	Medium	
c)	Low	

6.2. Do you think currently SMEs have contributed to poverty reduction in Kiko t/c

ID	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Strongly agree		1
b)	Agree		2
c)	Disagree		3
d)	Strongly disagree		4

6.3. What do you think should be done to reduce poverty in Kiko t/c?

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7.0. Health care services

7.1. We get health care services from clinics at cheaper cost compared to big hospitals.

ID	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Strongly agree		1
b)	Agree		2
c)	Disagree		3
d)	Strongly disagree		4

7.2. The health sector in Kiko t/c is good due to the setting up of clinics

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

Objective 3. What are the challenges faced by the small and medium enterprises in Kiko T/C, Kabarole District?

8.0. Challenges SMEs face

8.1 Access to credit

8.1.1 Does your firm/business access credit (tick)

Id	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

8.1.2 What limits your business from accessing credit

ID	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Interest rates		1
b)	Lack of collateral/security		2
c)	Not registered		3
d)	Have no bank acc		4

8.2 Managerial skills

8.2.1 The firm has a good management?

ID	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Strongly agree		1
b)	Agree		2
c)	Disagree		3
d)	Strongly disagree		4

8.2.2. The business employs educated people with managerial skills.

ID	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Strongly agree		1
b)	Agree		2
c)	Disagree		3
d)	Strongly disagree		4

8.2.3. We train our employee to increase efficiency

	Response	Tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

8.3. in your opinion, do u think the challenges provided below are the major challenges to your business or Organisation? (tick)

- a) Access to credit
- b) Managerial skills
- c) Others

	Response	tick	Measure
a)	Yes		1
b)	No		2

8.2. If others, please specify

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8.3. What should be done to solve such problems?

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****Thank you so much for your time****